

1 **Preparation of adsorbed bismuth-based visible light photocatalytic materials and**
2 **their effects on the performance of cement-based materials**

3
4 **Abstract:** In order to better solve the problem of pollutant degradation in cement-
5 based materials, the BiVO₄ was introduced into the reconstruction of the water-
6 encountered MgAl-LDHs layer after calcination based on the memory effect of
7 MgAl-LDHs, and the highly adsorbable visible light photocatalytic material
8 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs was successfully prepared. The large specific surface area
9 layered structure of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs provides more active sites for cement
10 hydration, promotes the growth and development of crystal nuclei, and accelerates
11 cement hydration. Its nanofilling effect can optimize the microstructure and improve
12 the mechanical properties of the cement paste. However, the reduction in the number
13 of active species and heterogeneous defects caused by the addition of excessive
14 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs will weaken the above-mentioned promotion effect. In the self-
15 cleaning performance test, the specimens prepared by the coating method showed
16 better self-cleaning performance, and the degradation effect was close to that of
17 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs on methylene blue (MB) solution, which once again confirmed
18 that BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs has good chemical stability. In the durability of
19 photocatalytic efficiency test, the specimens prepared by the polyvinyl chloride
20 (PVC) film loading method performed better. The above two performance tests show
21 that the number of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs molecules on the paste surface plays a major
22 role in the degradation of MB solution.

23 **Keywords:** cement-based materials; adsorbable visible light photocatalytic material;
24 BiVO₄; MgAl-LDHs; self-cleaning

25 **Abbreviations:** MB, Methylene blue; PVC, Polyvinyl chloride; TC, Tetracycline;
26 LDHs, Layered double hydroxides; SEM, Transmission electron microscope; XRD,
27 X-ray diffractometer; MIP, Mercury intrusion porosimeter; TGA, Thermogravimetric
28 analyzer; MgAl-LDHs, Magnesium aluminum hydrotalcite; CH, Calcium hydroxide;
29 AFm, Monosulfurized calcium sulfoaluminate; AFt, Calcium sulfonate; C₃S,
30 Tricalcium silicate; C-S-H, Calcium silicate hydrate; C₂S, Dicalcium silicate.

31 **1. Introduction**

32 Cement-based materials have become the most widely used building materials in
33 the world due to their good engineering properties and low cost [1-3]. However,
34 organic or inorganic pollutants such as Cl₂, H₂S, NO_x, and suspended particles
35 suspended in the air are easily attached to the outer surface of cement-based materials,
36 causing surface pollution. Long-term accumulation of pollutants will affect the
37 service life of cement-based materials. Researchers have tried to use biological
38 methods, physical/chemical adsorption methods, Fenton process, etc. [4] to treat
39 pollutants, but these traditional treatment methods cannot be widely used due to their
40 high cost, complex process, and poor selectivity for organic pollutants [5].
41 Semiconductor photocatalytic technology plays a vital role in solar energy conversion
42 and environmental protection due to its mild reaction conditions, high degradation
43 efficiency, and ability to avoid secondary pollution [6].

44 As the first generation of photocatalyst, the TiO₂ has the advantages of low cost,

45 high chemical stability, strong oxidative and reductive properties, and abundant
46 natural reserves [7-10] and is widely used in cement-based materials, and has
47 achieved good results. Wang et al. [11] synthesized nano-dispersed anatase TiO₂
48 hydrosol by hydrolysis and coated it on the surface of cement paste to prepare
49 photocatalytic cement paste, and tested the degradation of rhodamine B and NO_x by
50 the paste under ultraviolet light. The results showed that compared with commercial
51 nano-TiO₂ powder, TiO₂ hydrosol-modified cement paste showed better
52 photocatalytic performance and self-cleaning performance. Jiang et al. [12] loaded
53 nano-TiO₂ hydrosol on natural sand to explore the effect of this method on the
54 mechanical properties and photocatalytic properties of cement mortar. It was found
55 that compared with the blank control group, the 28 d compressive strength of TiO₂
56 hydrosol-modified cement paste increased by 67%. The degradation rates of RhB and
57 NO of TiO₂@Sand-enhanced mortar were 40% and 25% higher than those of TiO₂
58 powder-enhanced mortar, respectively. Xu et al. [13] added TiO₂@CoAl-LDH to
59 cement paste at 1%, 2%, and 4% of the weight of cement. The results showed that the
60 appropriate amount of TiO₂@CoAl-LDH added can make the cement paste have
61 better photocatalytic performance. However, it can only respond in the ultraviolet
62 region and has a low utilization rate of sunlight due to the large band gap of TiO₂
63 (3.2eV)[14]. In addition, the rapid recombination of photogenerated carriers of TiO₂
64 also reduces the photocatalytic performance[15], thus limiting its application in real
65 life.

66 In order to broaden the light response range of photocatalytic cement-based

67 materials and maximize the use of solar energy, researchers have tried to introduce
68 bismuth-based photocatalytic materials into cement-based materials and achieved
69 good results [16-18]. The BiVO₄ has good performance in photoelectrochemical
70 applications because of its regular crystal morphology, large specific surface area and
71 narrow band gap [19, 20] and is considered to be the second generation of
72 photocatalyst after TiO₂. Similar to the limitations of most photocatalysts, due to the
73 low degree of separation of photogenerated electron-hole pairs, they are prone to
74 agglomeration under the action of electrostatic forces and van der Waals forces,
75 making it difficult for pure BiVO₄ to fully exert its photocatalytic performance
76 advantages [21, 22]. Adsorption and photocatalysis always go hand in hand[23], but
77 the BiVO₄ has poor adsorption performance, which restricts its promotion and use in
78 real life[24-26]. Researchers [25, 27] have found that fixing the catalyst by an
79 adsorptive carrier is an effective means to overcome the above problems. The
80 adsorptive carrier adsorbs pollutants to the surface of BiVO₄, thereby increasing the
81 probability of contact between pollutants and active substances. Wang et al. [27]
82 combined highly adsorbable carbon spheres with BiVO₄ and successfully prepared a
83 composite material with excellent adsorption and photocatalytic properties. The
84 visible light catalytic degradation rates of methylene blue and rhodamine B of the
85 composite material were 11.56 times and 4.42 times that of pure BiVO₄, respectively.
86 Shi et al. [25] used a hydrothermal method to coat BiVO₄ on the adsorptive material
87 Pal and successfully prepared the composite material BiVO₄-Pal. When the
88 illumination time was 240 min, the catalytic degradation rate of BiVO₄-Pal on

89 tetracycline (TC) was 1.4 times that of pure BiVO₄, and it was still able to maintain
90 good photocatalytic performance after 4 high-temperature cycles of calcination.

91 Layered double hydroxides (LDHs), also known as hydrotalcites, have the
92 general formula: $[M_{(1-x)}^{(2+)}M_x^{(3+)}(OH)_2][A_{(x/n)}]^{n-} \cdot mH_2O$, where M²⁺, M³⁺, and Aⁿ⁻
93 represent divalent cations, trivalent cations, and interlayer anions, respectively [28].
94 The special structure of LDHs is formed by the electrostatic force between positively
95 charged brucite octahedrons and interlayer anions [29]. LDHs have attracted much
96 attention in the field of photocatalysis due to their stable layered structure, large
97 specific surface area, strong adsorption capacity, and adjustable band gap [30-32].
98 They are ideal materials for photocatalysts[33], catalyst carriers[34], and
99 adsorbents[35]. When composited with other semiconductor materials, MgAl-LDHs
100 particles can act as a barrier layer for the recombination of electronic charges and
101 capture sites, achieving better spatial charge separation [36]. Yang et al. [35] found
102 that adsorption materials such as activated carbon, bentonite, and fly ash have low
103 adsorption capacity and are difficult to recycle. LDHs not only have strong adsorption
104 properties, but can also photocatalytically degrade adsorbed organic pollutants,
105 thereby achieving the reuse of adsorbents. In addition, the memory effect is also an
106 important characteristic of LDHs. Studies have found that LDHs (LDO) calcined at
107 high temperatures have a memory effect. When exposed to water, they can restore
108 their parent structure through layer reconstruction [37] and introduce oxygen and
109 metal vacancy defects to the parent structure [38]. The generation of defects can not
110 only reduce the bandgap width and expand the light absorption range, but also
111 promote the separation of photogenerated carriers.

112 In order to solve the above research deficiencies, this study first combined the

113 strongly adsorbent MgAl-LDHs with the visible light catalyst BiVO₄ to prepare an
114 adsorption-type visible light catalytic composite material, and introduced it into
115 cement-based materials. Secondly, transmission electron microscope (SEM), X-ray
116 diffractometer (XRD), mercury intrusion porosimeter (MIP), thermogravimetric
117 analyzer (TGA) and other experimental methods were used to explore the effect of the
118 addition of photocatalytic composite materials on fresh cement and hardened cement
119 paste. Finally, the self-cleaning performance and durability of photocatalytic
120 efficiency of the cement paste modified by the composite photocatalytic material were
121 tested, and its self-cleaning mechanism was revealed. This provides a reference for
122 the research on visible light self-cleaning plain concrete.

123 **2. Materials and methods**

124 *2.1. Materials*

125 Magnesium aluminum hydrotalcite (MgAl-LDHs) is white powder, and its
126 molecular formula is CH₂₄Al₂Mg₆O₂₃ (molecular weight 603.98, analytical grade AR,
127 CAS number 11097-59-9), which purchased from Guangdong Wengjiang Chemical
128 Reagent Co., Ltd., China. Bismuth vanadate (BiVO₄) is bright yellow powder
129 (molecular weight 323.92, metal purity 99.9%, CAS number 14059-33-7), which
130 purchased from Shanghai Dingyun Reagent Business Department, China. Methylene
131 blue (MB) is dark green bronze luster powder (molecular formula C₁₆H₁₈C₁N₃S·3H₂O,
132 molecular weight 373.9, in line with corporate standards). It purchased from Wuxi
133 Yatai United Chemical Co., Ltd., China. Cement which is Conch brand ordinary
134 silicate cement (P.O42.5), which purchased from Ningbo Xiangshan County Conch

135 Cement Co., Ltd., China. The water used for the synthesis of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ was
136 deionized water, and the water used for other experiments was tap water in Ningbo,
137 China. The experimental reagents used in this study were not further purified.

138 2.2. Preparation of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$

139 Figure 1 shows the preparation process of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$. First, an
140 appropriate amount of MgAl-LDHs powder was weighted and poured it into a
141 crucible. Then, the crucible was placed in the center of the muffle furnace. The muffle
142 furnace was heated to 300 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min, and the calcination was
143 continued at 300 °C for 5 h, and then the calcination was stopped. After the powder
144 was cooled to room temperature, the calcined MgAl-LDHs (MgAl-LDO) was taken
145 out. Secondly, an appropriate amount of deionized water was measured and poured it
146 into a 1000 mL beaker, and BiVO_4 and MgAl-LDO were added into the beaker filled
147 with deionized water respectively, and then the beaker was placed on a magnetic
148 stirrer and stirred well for 6 h. Finally, the beaker was transferred to a drying oven at
149 105 °C. After drying, the beaker was taken out and cooled it to room temperature. The
150 sample was grinded into powder with an agate grinder to obtain the composite
151 material ($\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$) used in this study.

152
153 **Figure 1.** Schematic diagram of the synthesis of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs.

154 *2.3. Preparation of photocatalytic cement paste*

155 Figure 2 shows the preparation process of photocatalytic cement paste. The
156 water-cement ratio used in this study was 0.4. Water and cement was added into a
157 cement mortar mixer for mixing, and stirred for 120 s at low and high speeds
158 respectively. After stirring, the obtained cement paste was poured into three molds
159 with sizes of 100 mm×100 mm×50 mm. A PVC film was laid on the bottom of one of
160 the molds. They were then placed on a vibration table for vibration and compaction,
161 and the sample surface was covered with plastic wrap. After the specimens were cured
162 in the laboratory for 1 d and then were demolded. The mixed solution of
163 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs was sprayed on the surface of another specimen. Finally, the
164 above three test blocks were transferred to a standard curing room (temperature of
165 20±2 °C, relative humidity greater than 95%) for curing until the curing time
166 requirement of 7 d was met, and the above three test blocks was taken out for self-
167 cleaning performance testing.

Figure 2. (a) PVC film loading method; (b) Surface spraying method.

2.4. Characterization

A transmission electron microscope (SEM) of model tecnai F20 was used to test the morphology and structure of cement paste at different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages and curing ages. An X-ray diffractometer (XRD) of model D8 Advance was used with a test range of 10~80° and a scanning speed of 2 °/min to analyze the material composition and crystal structure of cement paste samples at different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages and curing ages. An AUTOPORE 9600 mercury intrusion porosimeter (MIP) was used with a pore size range of 0~100 nm, a porosity of 10%~50%, and a specified pressure of 30 psi. This was used to determine the pore structure of cement paste at different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages and curing ages. A NETZSCH TG 209F3 thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) was used to test the weight loss and differential weight loss of cement paste at different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDH dosages and curing ages.

According to the technical specification of “Test methods for water requirement

184 of normal consistency, setting time and soundness of the portland cement” (GB/T
185 1346-2011), the experiment was conducted to explore the effect of BiVO₄/MgAl-
186 LDHs on the physical properties of cement paste. A cement automatic flexural and
187 compressive testing machine with a loading rate of 2.4 kN/s was used according to the
188 technical specification of “Method of testing cements--Determination of strength”
189 (GB/T 17671-2021). The final value of the compressive strength of the cement paste
190 was the average values of the compressive strength of the three specimens in the same
191 group. The above operations were used to explore the effect of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs
192 on the mechanical properties of cement paste. First, the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs
193 suspension was obtained after ultrasonic treatment, and the suspension was fully
194 mixed with cement and poured into an ampoule. Secondly, the ampoule was
195 transferred to a constant temperature bath with a constant temperature of
196 ±0.00001 °C/24h. Finally, TAM assistant software was used to monitor the heat
197 release rate and cumulative heat release of cement within 72 h to explore the effect of
198 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs on the hydration heat of cement.

199 *2.5. Self-cleaning performance test*

200 A 50 mg/L MB solution was evenly sprayed on the surface of the test block, and
201 then the test block was transferred to a dark environment for 20 min to explore the
202 adsorption on the MB solution. After completing the above dark absorption stage, the
203 test block that had completed the adsorption-desorption equilibrium was placed under
204 a xenon lamp to enter the photocatalytic degradation stage. The xenon lamp working
205 current was 20 A, and a 400 nm filter was installed at the same time.

Figure 3. (a) Specimen test point ;(b) Specimen inspection.

206

207

208 The specific detection steps were as follows: The selection of test points and the

209 test operation of the specimens were shown in Figure 3. The color change of the

210 specimens in this test phase was measured by a colorimeter. At the same time, 5 and 9

211 test points were selected on the surface of the cement paste and the plain concrete,

212 respectively. The value of each group of test points was determined by the average

213 value of the above test points. Before spraying the MB solution, the test standard was

214 established on the cement paste and the surface of the plain concrete in the original

215 state. The test values at this time were L_0' , a_0' , and b_0' . After spraying the MB

216 solution, the colorimeter was taken out for detection. The test values at this time were

217 L_0 , a_0 , and b_0 . After reaching the 20 min adsorption-equilibrium state, the test values

218 at this time were L_1 , a_1 , and b_1 . The values at time t when entering the visible light

219 catalytic stage were L_t , a_t , and b_t . The adsorption rate ΔEI of 20 min and the visible

220 light catalytic degradation rate $R_{\Delta E_t}$ at time t were shown in equations (1) to (5).

$$\Delta E_0 = \sqrt{(L_0 - L_0')^2 + (a_0 - a_0')^2 + (b_0 - b_0')^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta E_1 = \sqrt{(L_1 - L_0')^2 + (a_1 - a_0')^2 + (b_1 - b_0')^2} \quad (2)$$

$$R_{\Delta E_1} = (\Delta E_0 - \Delta E_1) / \Delta E_0 \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta E_t = \sqrt{(L_t - L_0')^2 + (a_t - a_0')^2 + (b_t - b_0')^2} \quad (4)$$

$$R_{\Delta E_t} = (\Delta E_1 - \Delta E_t) / \Delta E_1 \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

221 Where, L_0' —black and white value in the original state; a_0' —red and green value in
 222 the original state; b_0' —yellow and blue value in the original state; L_0 —black and
 223 white value after spraying MB solution; a_0 —red and green value after spraying MB
 224 solution; b_0 —yellow and blue value after spraying MB solution; L_t —black and white
 225 value in adsorption-equilibrium state; a_t —red and green value in adsorption-
 226 equilibrium state; b_t —yellow and blue value in adsorption-equilibrium state; L_t —
 227 black and white value at visible light irradiation time t; a_t —red and green value at
 228 visible light irradiation time t; b_t —yellow and blue value at visible light irradiation
 229 time t.

230 2.6. Durability of photocatalytic performance

231 Figure 4 shows the stripping and the flushing process in the durability of
 232 photocatalytic performance durability test. A commercial wide tape was pasted on the
 233 surface of the cement paste and fully compacted. After staying for 10 s, the tape was
 234 torn off (Figure 4(a)). The above operation was repeated 3 times using a new tape.
 235 Figure 4(b) shows the flushing process in the durability of photocatalytic performance
 236 test. A stable water flow tap water outlet was directed to the surface of the
 237 photocatalytic cement paste for flushing. The flushing time was 5 min.

238

239

Figure 4. (a) Stripping; (b) Flushing.

240 **3. Results and discussion**

241 *3.1. Effect of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs on fresh cement paste*

242 *3.1.1. Morphological structure*

243 Figure 5 shows the SEM images of cement pastes with different BiVO₄/MgAl-
 244 LDHs dosages (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%) after curing for 3, 7, and 28 d. When the curing age
 245 is 3 d, the pores formed by the accumulation of hexagonal calcium hydroxide (CH)
 246 and petal-shaped monosulfurized calcium sulfoaluminate (AFm) can be clearly
 247 observed. Due to the filling effect, the pore structure of the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs
 248 modified cement paste is more compact. However, when the dosage is 2% and 3%,
 249 the accumulation and agglomeration of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs weakens the filling
 250 effect. As the cement hydration proceeds, when the curing age is 7 d, the
 251 microstructure of the samples becomes more compact, and CH develops from
 252 hexagonal plates to well-oriented dense crystals. When the curing age is 28 d, the
 253 presence of radial calcium sulfonate (AFt) can be clearly observed. Compared with
 254 the control group, the incorporation of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs can also promote the

255 formation of lamellar dense phase calcite.

256 **Figure 5.** SEM images of cement paste after curing for 3, 7, and 28 d under different

257 $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ dosages.

258 3.1.2. Cement hydration heat

259 Figure 6a shows the evolution curve of cement hydration heat within 72 h at
260 different $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ dosages (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%). This stage is the
261 accelerated period of cement hydration. The peak value is mainly caused by the
262 dissolution heat of tricalcium silicate (C_3S) and the release heat of calcium silicate

263 hydrate (C-S-H) growth and development. Compared with the control group, the peak
264 value of the modified cement paste hydration heat is higher and the time to reach the
265 peak value is shorter. When the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosage is 1%, the peak value is
266 the largest and the time to reach the peak value is the shortest, which are 5.54 mW·g⁻¹
267 and 11.24 h respectively. It can be seen that the addition of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs
268 promotes the early hydration rate. Figure 6b shows the cumulative heat release of
269 cement hydration within 72 h at different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages (0%, 1%, 2%,
270 3%), with the total heat release being 248.6, 306.5, 299.9, and 273.4 J/g, respectively.
271 It can be seen that the hydration heat release of cement paste has been greatly
272 improved due to the introduction of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs. When the dosage is 1%, the
273 maximum increase is 23.3%. The reason for the above phenomenon is mainly that
274 cement hydration is affected by the surface characteristics of particles. Since
275 photocatalytic nanomaterials with large specific surface areas can provide more
276 nucleation sites, they stimulate the growth and development of crystals during the
277 nucleation process, thereby promoting the cement hydration process [39]. However,
278 when the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosage is too high, it will lead to the occurrence of
279 dilution effect, reducing the number of active species in cement paste, so that this
280 promotion effect will be limited [40].

281 **Figure 6.** (a) Cement hydration rate of cement paste at different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs
 282 dosages; (b) Cumulative heat release of cement paste at different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs
 283 dosages.

284 3.1.3. Cement hydration products

285 Figure 7 shows the XRD patterns of cement paste after curing for 3, 7, and 28 d
 286 under different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%). By comparison, it is
 287 found that the control group and the experimental group have similar mineral
 288 compositions and diffraction peaks, indicating that the addition of BiVO₄/MgAl-
 289 LDHs has no significant effect on the types of hydration products. C-S-H gels and CH
 290 are the main hydration products of dicalcium silicate (C₂S) and C₃S. However, since
 291 XRD patterns cannot successfully calibrate the amorphous peak of C-S-H gels, the
 292 peak intensity of CH is usually selected to measure the performance of cement paste.
 293 As cement hydration continues, the diffraction peak intensity of unhydrated C₂S and
 294 C₃S near 32°~33° gradually decreases, but the peak intensity of CH near 17.8°
 295 increases. Moreover, at the same curing age, the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs modified paste
 296 usually shows a higher diffraction intensity than the control group. The above
 297 phenomenon may be due to the fact that BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs, as a nanomaterial, has a

298 high specific surface area that can provide more nucleation sites for the hydration
 299 reaction [41], thereby promoting the cement hydration process. In addition, the calcite
 300 diffraction peak at around 29.2° increases with the increase of curing time. This is
 301 mainly due to the carbonation of CH or C-S-H during the preparation and curing of
 302 the paste. The diffraction peak intensity of the calcite in the modified paste at the
 303 same age is weaker, which may be related to the ability of MgAl-LDHs to effectively
 304 capture CO_2 [42].

305 **Figure 7.** XRD patterns of cement paste after curing for 3, 7, and 28 d under different
 306 $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ dosages.

307 Figure 8 shows the weight loss and differential weight loss curves of cement
 308 paste at different curing ages and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ dosages. It is not difficult to
 309 find that the different visible light catalytic material dosages at different curing ages
 310 have similar curve changes, which indicates that all samples at this curing age have

311 the same reaction during the thermal decomposition process. It is worth noting that
 312 although the addition of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ did not have a significant effect on the
 313 thermal decomposition process, the weight loss peaks at different ages still have
 314 relatively obvious differences. The emergence of this phenomenon is largely
 315 attributed to the fact that the addition of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ has changed the amount
 316 of cement hydration products.

317 **Figure 8.** Weight loss and differential weight loss curves of cement paste with
 318 different $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ dosages at 3, 7 and 28 d.

319 As shown in Figure 8, the weight loss peak areas of the paste samples at different
 320 curing ages are mainly concentrated in the following three stages: the first stage is
 321 between 30 and 200 °C, which is mainly due to the dehydration of C-S-H gel (L_f); the
 322 second stage is between 350 and 500 °C, which is mainly due to the dehydroxylation

323 of CH (L_s); the third stage is between 500 and 750 °C, which is mainly due to the
 324 decarbonation of calcite (L_t). The hydration degree β of all samples was calculated
 325 according to equations (6, 7), and the calculation results are shown in Table 1.

$$W_h = L_f + L_s + 0.41 \times L_t \quad (6)$$

$$\beta = \frac{W_h}{0.24} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

326 Where, W_h —chemically bound water, %; L_s —dehydroxylation of CH, %; L_t —
 327 decarbonation of calcite, %; L_f —dehydration of C-S-H gel, %; 0.41—conversion rate
 328 of chemically bound water in CH, %; 0.24—maximum value of chemically bound
 329 water after complete hydration, %.

330 **Table 1.** Hydration degree values of cement paste at 3, 7 and 28 d under different
 331 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages.

Curing age/d	0%	1%	2%	3%
3	42.16	45.18	43.45	43.43
7	47.95	50.53	50.18	48.78
28	58.39	59.79	59.51	59.46

332 Figure 9 shows the relationship between the cement hydration degree and the
 333 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosage (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%) at different curing ages (3 d, 7 d, 28
 334 d). As the curing age increases (3 d~28 d), the cement hydration degree also increases.
 335 The degree of hydration of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs modified cement at different curing
 336 ages is higher than that of the control group, and this improvement effect gradually
 337 weakens with the increase of curing age. However, with the increase of
 338 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosage, the corresponding degree of hydration first increases and
 339 then decreases. When the dosage is 1%, the degree of hydration is the highest at this

340 time, which is 7.2%, 5.4%, and 2.4% higher than that of the control group,
341 respectively. The main reasons for the above phenomenon are: (1) The appropriately
342 added $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ can provide more active sites, promote the growth of
343 crystal nuclei, and improve the degree of hydration; (2) When the dosage is too high,
344 this promoting effect will be weakened, which can be attributed to the delayed effect
345 of photocatalytic materials on cement hydration [43, 44].

346 **Figure 9.** The relationship between the cement hydration degree and the
347 $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ dosage under different curing ages.

348 3.1.4. Physical properties

349 According to the technical specification of "Test methods for water requirement
350 of normal consistency, setting time and soundness of the portland cement" (GB/T
351 1346-2011), different dosages (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%) of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ were added
352 to cement paste to explore the effect of the photocatalytic material on the water
353 requirement of normal consistency, setting time and soundness of the cement. The
354 specific operation steps are shown in the Section 2.4. The results are shown in Table 2
355 and Figure 10.

356 **Table 2.** Water requirement of normal consistency, setting time and soundness of the
 357 portland cement at different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages.

Dosage	Water requirement of normal consistency/%	Initial setting time/min	Final setting time/min	Soundness
0%	26.0	170	305	Qualified
1%	27.0	165	300	Qualified
2%	27.4	160	295	Qualified
3%	27.8	158	291	Qualified

358 **Figure 10.** (a) The relationship between the water requirement of normal consistency
 359 and the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosage; (b) The relationship between the setting time and
 360 the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosage.

361 When the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosage increases, the the water requirement of
 362 normal consistency of the cement also increases, as shown in Figure 10a. This is
 363 mainly because the MgAl-LDHs in the composite photocatalytic material has a strong
 364 adsorption capacity for water molecules, resulting in a larger water requirement of
 365 normal consistency with a larger dosage. Compared with the control group, the initial
 366 setting time and final setting time of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs modified cement paste are
 367 shorter (Figure 10b). This is mainly because the lamellar structure of BiVO₄/MgAl-
 368 LDHs with a large specific surface area can provide more active sites, promote the
 369 growth of crystal nuclei, thereby promoting the cement hydration process and

370 shortening the setting time.

371 3.2. Effect of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ on hardened cement paste

372 3.2.1. Pore structure

373 Figures 11 and 12 are the cumulative pore volume and differential pore size
374 distribution curves of hardened cement paste at different $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ dosages
375 and curing ages. The cumulative pore volume and differential pore size critical values
376 of all paste samples show a downward trend with the increase of curing age. This
377 phenomenon indicates that the improvement of pore structure is mainly dominated by
378 cement hydration, and the addition of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ has no obvious effect on it.

379 **Figure 11.** Cumulative pore volume of cement paste under different catalyst dosages
380 and curing ages.

381

382

383 **Figure 12.** Differential pore size distribution of cement paste under different catalyst
 384 dosage and curing ages.

385 In order to further explore the effect of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs on the pore structure
 386 of hardened cementitious materials, this study compares the porosity, average pore
 387 size, harmless pores, harmful pores and a small amount of harmful pores of hardened
 388 cement paste at different curing ages (3, 7, and 28 d) under different BiVO₄/MgAl-
 389 LDHs dosages (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%). Among them, the classification of hardened paste
 390 pores [44] can be divided into harmless pores (<50 nm), a small amount of harmful
 391 pores (50~200 nm) and harmful pores (>200 nm), and the results are shown in Table
 392 3. As the curing age increases (3, 7, and 28 d), the porosity and average pore size
 393 continue to decrease. This is mainly because the microstructure of the hardened paste
 394 becomes denser as the cement hydration process continues to advance. The harmful
 395 pore volume shows a trend of first increasing and then decreasing with the increase of
 396 curing age. When the dosage of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs is 1%, the harmful pore volume

397 is the smallest. Compared with the control group, the harmful pore volume decreased
 398 by 64.5%, 44.1%, and 30.7%, respectively. The reason for the above phenomenon is
 399 mainly due to the appropriate addition of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs, the microfiller effect is
 400 produced by the nano-photocatalytic material [45], which makes the microstructure of
 401 the hardened cement paste denser. When the dosage of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs is too
 402 high, it is very likely to cause the accumulation and agglomeration of nanoparticles
 403 [46], and the effect of the microfiller will be greatly weakened. In addition, the
 404 reduction degree of harmful pore volume gradually decreases with the increase of
 405 curing age, which is related to the weakening of microfiller effect as cement hydration
 406 proceeds[44].

407 **Table 3.** Porosity, average pore diameter and pore classification results of hardened
 408 modified cement paste.

Catalyst ratio/%	Curing age/d	Porosity/%	Average pore size/nm	Harmless pores/(mL/g)	A small amount of harmful pores/(mL/g)	Harmful pores/(mL/g)
0	3	35.13	46.70	0.064	0.090	0.062
	7	30.62	32.25	0.077	0.093	0.034
	28	25.94	27.21	0.078	0.053	0.026
1	3	28.27	47.11	0.065	0.094	0.022
	7	27.89	31.55	0.064	0.096	0.019
	28	22.78	27.11	0.066	0.058	0.018
2	3	33.25	39.78	0.069	0.110	0.040
	7	28.00	31.22	0.069	0.087	0.021
	28	24.16	29.68	0.065	0.066	0.020
3	3	35.06	33.81	0.059	0.105	0.061
	7	28.89	33.12	0.069	0.081	0.026
	28	24.49	29.24	0.063	0.068	0.024

409 *3.2.2. Mechanical properties*

410 In order to study the effect of adding BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs on the mechanical
 411 properties of hardened cement paste, BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs with dosages of 0%, 1%,
 412 2%, and 3% were added to the cement paste. After reaching the curing age (3, 7, and
 413 28 d), the compressive strength of the hardened cement paste with different
 414 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages was tested. The compressive strength values are shown
 415 in Table 4.

416 **Table 4.** Compressive strength of hardened cement paste with different BiVO₄/MgAl-
 417 LDHs content at various curing ages.

Catalyst ratio/%	3 d compressive strength/MPa	7 d compressive strength/MPa	28 d compressive strength/MPa
0	23.8	35.9	49.2
1	27.1	43.3	52.7
2	26.8	39.8	51.4
3	25.4	38.5	50.1

418 **Figure 13.** The relationship between the compressive strength of modified cement
 419 paste after curing for 3, 7, and 28 d and the dosage of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs.

420 Figure 13 shows the compressive strength of hardened cement paste at 3, 7, and
 421 28 d under different BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosages. As the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs dosage

422 increases, the compressive strength of the cement paste increases first and then
423 decreases. The compressive strength of the cement paste modified by the
424 photocatalytic material at each curing age is higher than that of the blank control
425 group. The compressive strength of the cement paste is the largest when the
426 $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDH}$ dosage is 1%. Compared with the control group, the compressive
427 strength of the cement paste at 3, 7, and 28 d increases by 13.9%, 20.6%, and 1.8%,
428 respectively. The photocatalytic material significantly improves the early compressive
429 strength. When the curing is 28 d, the improvement effect of compressive strength is
430 severely weakened. The reasons for the above phenomenon are as follows: (1) The
431 mechanical properties of hardened cementitious materials are related to their
432 microstructure. Compared with the control group, the harmful pores and porosity of
433 $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDH}$ modified cement paste are reduced. When the dosage is 1%, the
434 harmful pores and porosity are the lowest, so the compressive strength is the highest
435 at this time. As the dosage increases, the minimum harmful pores and porosity also
436 increase accordingly, and the compressive strength at 2% and 3% dosages begins to
437 decrease; (2) The addition of an appropriate amount of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDH}$ can refine
438 the pore structure, but excessive addition of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDH}$ s will cause
439 accumulation and agglomeration, resulting in heterogeneous defects in the
440 cementitious matrix, and the formation of an interface zone between the agglomerate
441 and the matrix, thereby promoting the generation and development of cracks [44].

442 *3.3. Self-cleaning performance of visible light catalytic cement paste*

443 *3.3.1. Self-cleaning performance*

444 Figure 14 shows the adsorption degradation rate and the visible light catalytic
445 degradation rate of the coating method, PVC film loading method and control group.
446 After 20 min of dark adsorption stage and 60 min of visible light catalytic stage, the
447 adsorption degradation rates of the three are 64.3%, 53.4% and 17.2%, respectively,
448 and the visible light catalytic degradation rates are 89.2%, 59.6% and 9.4%,
449 respectively. Compared with the control group, the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDH modified
450 cement paste shows better adsorption performance and visible light catalytic
451 performance, among which the sample prepared by the coating method has the best
452 adsorption-visible light catalytic performance. In the above test results, the control
453 group also has a certain amount of adsorption and visible light degradation
454 performance. This is mainly because in the dark adsorption stage, the typical porous
455 cement-based material can adsorb a certain amount of MB molecules, and then in the
456 visible light catalytic stage, due to the presence of photosensitization, the organic dye
457 MB molecules are decomposed. Secondly, the visible light catalytic composite
458 material BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs is sprayed on the surface of the test block still has
459 efficient adsorption-visible light catalytic performance, which is related to its good
460 chemical stability. In addition, the cement paste prepared by the PVC film loading
461 method can show relatively good adsorption-visible light catalytic performance,
462 mainly because the test block shows that a large amount of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs is
463 embedded, which improves its adsorption performance and visible light catalytic
464 performance.

465 **Figure 14.** Adsorption rate and visible light catalytic rate of cement paste under
 466 different modification methods.

467 *3.3.2. Durability of photocatalytic performance*

468 In actual working process, photocatalytic building materials are easily exposed to
 469 extreme external conditions such as rain flushing and physical wear, which has a great
 470 impact on their photocatalytic performance. In order to explore the performance
 471 durability of the prepared photocatalytic cement-based composite materials exposed
 472 to adverse external conditions, this study used tap water flushing and commercial tape
 473 stripping to simulate rain flushing and physical wear in real life.

474 *3.3.2.1. Stripping*

475 Figure 15 shows the adsorption degradation rate and the visible light catalytic
 476 degradation rate of the coating method, PVC film loading method and control group
 477 after stripping treatment. After 20 min of dark adsorption stage and 60 min of visible
 478 light catalytic stage, the adsorption degradation rates of the three are 59.8%, 52.1%
 479 and 20.5%, respectively, and the visible light catalytic degradation rates are 70.8%,
 480 57.8% and 10.3%, respectively. By comparing the adsorption performance and the
 481 visible light catalytic performance of the test blocks before and after stripping

482 treatment, it is not difficult to find that the stripping treatment has the greatest impact
 483 on the modified test blocks with surface coating, and the adsorption rate and the
 484 visible light catalytic rate are reduced by 4.5% and 18.3%, respectively. This is mainly
 485 due to the poor adhesion between the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs and the paste surface,
 486 which is caused by the large loss of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs after external stripping.
 487 However, for the paste blocks under the PVC film method and the control group, the
 488 stripping treatment failed to significantly change the pore structure of the surface, and
 489 the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs molecules embedded in the block surface can still function
 490 normally.

491 **Figure 15.** Adsorption rate and visible light catalytic rate of modified cement paste
 492 after stripping treatment.

493 3.3.2.2. Flushing

494 Figure 16 shows the adsorption degradation rate and visible light catalytic
 495 degradation rate of the coating method, PVC film loading method and control group
 496 after stripping and flushing treatment. After 20 min of dark adsorption stage and 60
 497 minutes of visible light catalytic stage, the adsorption degradation rates of the three
 498 are 44.8%, 49.5% and 16.3%, respectively, and the visible light catalytic degradation

499 rates are 52.3%, 55.4% and 8.2%, respectively. Compared with the stripping
 500 treatment, the cement paste performance of the control group and the PVC loading
 501 film method is not significantly affected after continued flushing treatment. This is
 502 mainly because $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ can be firmly embedded in the hardened
 503 substrate, thereby ensuring that the modified paste has excellent adsorption-visible
 504 light catalytic performance. However, the photocatalytic cement paste prepared by
 505 coating method after stripping treatment is more susceptible to flushing. This is
 506 mainly because the adhesion between the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ and the substrate is
 507 relatively weak. When the sample is rinsed by water, it is very easy to fall off. Its
 508 adsorption-photocatalytic performance is greatly affected.

509 **Figure 16.** Adsorption rate and visible light catalytic rate of modified cement paste
 510 after stripping and flushing.

511 3.3.3. Mechanism of visible light photocatalytic degradation

512 This section takes the photocatalytic cement paste prepared by the PVC film
 513 loading method as an example to analyze the visible light catalytic mechanism. Since
 514 the nanomaterial $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MgAl-LDHs}$ has a certain filling effect, some photocatalyst
 515 molecules are filled in the pores during the specimen preparation process. Another

516 part of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs is covered by or embedded in the hydration product, as
 517 shown in Figure 17. When the self-cleaning performance test was performed, the self-
 518 cleaning performance of the cement paste modified by the PVC film method was
 519 between the control group and the surface spraying method. This is mainly because
 520 the number of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs molecules that can directly contact the MB
 521 solution is between the control group and the surface spraying method. However, the
 522 photocatalytic cement paste prepared by the spraying method will lose a large amount
 523 of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs after the external effects of stripping and flushing, while the
 524 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs distributed on the surface of the PVC film method specimen are
 525 more stable. The degradation of MB solution by photocatalytic cement paste mainly
 526 goes through the following stages: MB molecules are adsorbed by the visible light
 527 photocatalytic material BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs and the pores on the surface of the
 528 specimen in the dark environment. The BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs molecules are
 529 successfully excited, releasing photogenerated holes with oxidation and
 530 photogenerated electrons with reduction, when it is irradiated by visible light. Under
 531 this redox reaction, O₂ is reduced to ·O₂⁻ and H₂O is oxidized to ·OH. Finally, MB is
 532 degraded to H₂O and CO₂ under the joint action of the above active substances.

534 **Figure 17.** Mechanism of visible light photocatalytic degradation of MB solution by
535 cement paste.

536 **6. Conclusions**

537 This article firstly composited highly adsorbable MgAl-LDHs with visible light
538 catalyst BiVO₄ to successfully prepare highly adsorbable-visible light catalytic
539 composite BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs. Secondly, the effect of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs on fresh
540 cement paste and hardened cement paste was further explored. Finally, the self-
541 cleaning property and performance durability of photocatalytic cement paste were
542 tested. The main research conclusions are as follows:

543 (1) Based on the memory effect, the BiVO₄ was introduced into the
544 reconstruction of the water-encountered MgAl-LDHs layer after high-temperature
545 calcination, and a high adsorption-visible light catalytic composite material
546 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs was prepared by a simple, efficient, economical and
547 environmentally friendly method.

548 (2) The BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs was added to cement to explore its effect on fresh
549 cement paste and hardened cement paste. The results show that the large specific
550 surface area lamellar structure of BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs can provide more active sites
551 for cement hydration, promote the growth of crystal nuclei, accelerate the cement
552 hydration process, and shorten the setting time. The nanofilling effect of
553 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs can improve the pore structure and enhance the mechanical
554 properties of cement paste. However, when the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs is excessively
555 added, the dilution effect and heterogeneous defects will weaken the above-mentioned

556 promotion effect.

557 (3) Compared with the cement paste modified by the PVC film loading method
558 and the blank control group, the cement paste prepared by the coating method has
559 better self-cleaning performance. However, due to the weak adhesion between
560 BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs and the substrate, after stripping and flushing, the BiVO₄/MgAl-
561 LDHs coating on the surface of the specimen fell off in large quantities, and the self-
562 cleaning performance was greatly affected. But for the cement paste prepared by the
563 PVC film loading method, the BiVO₄/MgAl-LDHs can be firmly embedded in the
564 surface of the specimen, so it can still show good photocatalytic efficiency and
565 durability under extremely harsh external conditions.

566 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

567 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or
568 personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this
569 paper.

570 **Data availability**

571 Data will be made available on request.

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